

Table 1: The 62 articles used in the study.

Title	ID
Programming as a Woman in Tech	A1
What I wish, as a woman in tech, I knew early on?	A2
Reflections on my career as a woman in tech.	A3
Because You Are a Woman.	A4
The Typecast Tango: Avoiding the Frontend Label as a Woman In Tech.	A5
The incredible weight of being a trans woman in tech.	A6
Sometimes I Feel Like I'm Invisible - Experiences of a Woman in Tech.	A7
I am a Woman in Tech.	A8
Being a Woman in Tech: My Journey.	A9
Yes, I am a developer, and yes, I am a woman.	A10
Be a yes-woman.	A11
What it Means to be a Woman in Tech in 2019.	A12
Nevertheless, It Still Sucks To Be A Woman In Tech.	A13
So...this is what it's like being a woman in tech?	A14
The first French computer science thesis author was... a woman, Marion Créhange(but nobody knows)	A15
Developer world as a woman.	A16
HerCode: Tips for negotiating compensation as a woman in tech.	A17
Boosting Woman Participation in Open Source Projects: A Beginner's Guide to Contributing.	A18
Career in Tech: Why Bother If You're Female?	A19
On the role of female coders in software development.	A20
How is it to be a female programmer in the tech world?	A21
Could your recruitment process be discouraging female developers?	A22
Persisting Past Dissonance: Adapting to the Identity of a Female Developer.	A23
4 annoyances of being a female developer (and how to help to make it better)	A24
What it's like to be a technical female founder of a mobile app.	A25
Taking the perspective of a female dev.	A26
Why Are There So Few Female Software Developers?	A27
Being a Female Programmer: How is it For You?	A28
Why are there fewer female developers?	A29
Why do we have more male applicants than female ones?	A30
What must we do to encourage more female coders?	A31
The Future (of AI) is Female: How Hiring Bias Mitigation in NLP Can Be Great for Women Now and in the Future.	A32
5 Things I've Learned as a Female Developer	A33
Becoming a female software engineer (who studied Geography)	A34
To The Young Female Software Engineer With Her First Job Offer	A35
Things a female dev who has been in the industry for 16 years has to say	A36
6 tips: Finding your balance as a mother and software engineer	A37
Promoting Gender Equity and Inclusion in the Tech Industry and Beyond	A38
How Age, Race, and Gender Affect Software Engineering Pay	A39
Gender Equality in Tech: Breaking Barriers and Building a Better Future	A40
I am proud to be a transgender IT developer	A41
Transgender Tech	A42
Normalizing Maternity in Tech	A43
Women in tech: Being a developer and a mom	A44
Creating Tight Cohesive Tech Teams for Women to Thrive	A45
Tackling the Lack of Women in Technology	A46
Box, Facebook, and Pinterest Announced WEST Program for Women	A47
ThoughtWorks Recognized as Most Women-Friendly Tech Company	A48
QConSF: Is Managing Men and Women Really That Different?	A49
Addressing Gender Imbalance in Software Engineering Through	A50
Addressing Gender Imbalance in Software Engineering Through	A51
Q and A on the Book Good Guys	A52
The Future of Work Is Female	A53
The Journey from Underrepresented IC to CTO: How Open Source Helped	A54
I'd Hire More Women If They Would Apply!	A55
Is Managing Men and Women Really That Different?	A56
Women in AI and Blockchain	A57
The Evolution of Engineering Culture: Oh, the Places We've Been	A58
Women in Agile and the Confidence Code	A59
Debunking the Steve Rule	A60
Woman in Agile	A61
Diversity and Inclusion in Tech: A Panel Discussion	A62